

Human-Centered solutions based on automated visual inspection system

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Abstract. Conventional painting inspections in the wind industry rely on human labour to visually inspect the parts, and the mental and physical fatigue of the operator influences the accuracy. The advances introduced on camera sensors, robots, and artificial intelligence algorithms can create a collaborative working environment between operators and automated visual inspection system.

One of the main challenges for the automatic painting inspection system is the integration with autonomous guided vehicle to perform the inspection routes, and the communication of the data generated during the inspection (defect detection, location, etc.) to the augmented reality platform to send the specific information to the operator to perform the painting repairing operation.

Current research aims to define a framework where integrating non-destructive inspection technologies, autonomous guided vehicles, and augmented reality will allow a symbiotic collaboration between humans and robots. The interoperability between these three solutions will increase the Human-Robot Collaboration in a wind tower painting process, improving product quality assurance.

Keywords: Quality inspection · surface defects · non-destructive inspection · Human-Robot Collaboration · Zero Defects.

1 Introduction

Integrating non-destructive inspection solutions, based on Zero Defects and Zero Waste (ZDZW) strategies, requires collaborative networks to develop the technology needed to deploy in industrial environments. The EU industry's digital transformation to enhance manufacturing competitiveness and resilience demands the reduction of material and energy consumption [1]. New quality assurance policies based on integrating Non-Destructive Inspection Technologies (NDIT) will sustain these ZDZW

strategies [2]. Collaboration between technological providers, research centres, universities, and industrial companies in a collaborative network provides a competitive framework for developing non-destructive inspection solutions for quality assurance.

Improving production efficiency and sustainability relies on a digital transformation of the manufacturing quality assurance policies. Several enabling technologies (safety, data sharing, sensors, etc.) require that subject matter experts engage in collaboration networks to integrate in-process inspection solutions based on ZDZW strategies [3], [4], [5]. The manufacturing companies that integrate ZDZW solutions in their production systems will present a competitive advantage since the reprocessing, rework, or inspection workload will be reduced. Automated visual inspection system, based on Zero Defect Manufacturing (ZDM), focus on performing quality inspection that are conventionally execute manually by trained operators [6].

Recent sensor, software and robotics developments require that industrial and technological providers engage in collaborative networks to create autonomous visual inspection systems. The advances introduced on camera sensors, robots, and artificial intelligence algorithms can create a collaborative working environment between operators and automated visual inspection systems. The current article aims to develop a framework for interoperability between different technologies required to implement an automated visual inspection system, focusing their efforts on the social sustainability of the solution developed.

1.1 Wind renewable energy

In the past two years, the energy and manufacturing sector has been shaken by the record on gas prices (around 100 Euro/MWh), historically below 30 Euro/MWh. The Russian invasion of Ukraine and the geological tensions with gas producers have produced an increase in gas and diesel prices, which, in the mid or long-term, has affected the logistic cost, parts manufacturing and food production, which has caused inflation values not seen in more than three decades (European Central Bank, 2022; United Nations, 2022).

The European commission has proposed to increase the energy generation capacities up to 1236 GW by 2030, through the Renewable Energy Directive. In particular, Wind energy represents one the main sector for the REPowerEU energy objectives, since it is a stable, abundant resource with elevated public acceptance [9]. From 2020, the European Union has invested around 30 billion euros to foster wind energy production, but to achieve 2030 targets, it is estimated to rise above 60 billion before the end of the current decade. This support will be provided by the InvestEU programme, the private sector and the European Investment Bank (EIB) [10], [11].

The wind renewable energy supply chain comprises several stakeholders, such as wind turbine manufacturers, companies that manufacture the towers or blades, cable suppliers, and electrical companies that manage and exploit wind farms. The renewable energy sector employs more than 1.5 million people annually in the European Union, composed of hundreds of suppliers, generating annual turnover higher than 158 billion euros [12]. Some of the most dominant countries in the European Union are Austria,

Czech Republic, France, Germany and Spain. The development and integration of new technologies, combined with digitalization, will reduce production costs and drive Europe producers in the energy transition required to achieve the Climate Target Plan and European Green Deal to climate neutrality by 2050. Several scenarios are drafted to achieve deep decarbonisation of all sectors of the economy based on the 2050 net-zero emissions objectives; in all of them, a significant increase in renewable production sources (wind, solar, and hydropower) will be required [13].

Based on the 2030 climate target plan, greenhouse gas emissions should be reduced by more than 50% by 2030 compared to 1990 emissions. To achieve this milestone, renewable energy will play a relevant role in the EU's energy strategy. Currently, the offshore installed capacity is estimated at 12 GW; by 2030, the scale-up should reach 60 GW. Furthermore, to be aligned with the 2050 climate-neutrality and zero pollution goals, the offshore wind installed capacity should reach 300 GW. This massive change in the energy sector in less than 30 years is estimated to require more than 800 billion euros [14]. Operators currently carry out wind tower paint inspection manually; the article proposes a framework to facilitate human-robot collaboration, aiming to enhance interoperability between three solutions: automatic visual inspection technologies, autonomous guided vehicles and augmented reality, to perform automatic visual inspection. By reducing inspection cycle times and lead times, improving reliability, reducing manual labour, cutting operational costs, and enhancing the resilience and competitiveness of the EU wind energy sector.

1.2 Quality policies based in non-destructive inspection technologies

Quality assurance policies guarantee that the items or parts are manufactured in conformity with customer or regulatory requirements. Conventional visual inspection methodologies rely on human labour, in order to detect and classify defects. Conventional visual inspection processes a trained operator performs the inspection to detect pits, holes, scratches, or other defects. The wind tower inspection surface ranges from 500-2.500 m²; this vast area requires elevated inspection times, which may end in operator physical or mental fatigue.

In all manufacturing processes, when the process shifts from an in-control state to an out-of-control, the occurrence of defective parts may increase [15]. Coating defects in the wind tower painting process may decrease the steel's chemical resistance to withstand the service's environmental conditions. The inspection policies can be improved by deploying automatic visual inspection equipment, minimising the dispatch of defective products, and improving warranty periods. In the wind energy sector, the warranty periods are important since the warranty cost of offshore wind towers can present elevated costs in repair, labour, and replacement activities.

2 Social sustainability in quality assurance

The human-centered solutions based automated visual inspection system can create a safe, dynamic, and real-time decision-making for a collaborative working environment between humans and robots. The development of new optical sensors, artificial

intelligence algorithms, and communication protocols for automatic visual inspection systems allows to implement in-process inspection performed by robot systems in safe conditions (Wang et al., 2020).

Integrating advanced control solutions in autonomous guided vehicles based on machine vision and LIDAR permits operators and robotic systems to share a physical space without barriers, performing coordinated and synchronous activities. Thanks to the integration of the safety features, the physical workload is reduced, and the operator's working conditions are enhanced. In this collaborative environment, the automatic inspection visual inspection system performs the repetitive tasks of visual inspection of the wind tower, and the operator repairs the defects thanks to the information provided by the augmented reality solution.

2.1 Workers physical and psychological wellbeing

The human factors involved in conventional inspection policies rely on manual inspection and may present an elevated workload affecting the physical and psychological operators' well-being. Also, the training on quality criteria's is time-consuming activity, which may lead to increase lead times and production costs [16]. It should take into account that the cognitive engagement of operators is depleted when repetitive task is performed during the shift. In the new scenario proposed the physical and psychological workers wellbeing will be improved, since displacement required to inspect the part, and the visual inspection will be performed by the automatic inspection system. Repetitive and monotonous movements or long-time postures, common in manual industries, can lead to work-related musculoskeletal disorders [17]. Integrating autonomous guided vehicles, augmented reality, and artificial vision on an automatic inspection system, which can work in a collaborative environment due to the safety features installed, will allow for the improvement of the level of automation of the wind tower painting process. Combining several sensors and technologies for inspection and navigation, the robotic systems in complementing competencies can improve ergonomics, working conditions and process performance.

2.2 Symbiotic human-robot collaboration

Collaboration involves joint goal-oriented activities, sharing capabilities, competencies, and resources [18]. Human-Robot Collaborative working environments or automatic visual inspection systems involve three main design factors: safety, optimized task distribution, and human-robot interaction/adaptive control, compared to traditional isolated robotic cells.

The safety of automatic visual inspection systems will be supported by advanced technologies, such as machine vision algorithms and RGB optical and LIDAR sensors, which have successfully integrated into Robotic Operative Systems (ROS) of the autonomous guided vehicle (AGV) [16]. This innovative inspection approach reduces the exposition to chemical agents and manual labour, enhancing safety, creating a more ergonomic inspection process, and collaborative scenario.

2.3 Sustainable performance indicators for painting inspection

The wind tower painting inspection process involves elevated surfaces being inspected with small defects; eye strain is a significant human factor that emphasises the potential for increased operator mental fatigue. Also to cover the inspection of the all-tower large distances are covered, these actions involves repetitive and monotonous movements that can lead to work-related musculoskeletal disorders. The proposed automatic visual inspection system focuses on developing symbiotic human-robot collaboration to improve manufacturing performance and ergonomics.

Table 1: Painting inspection social sustainability objectives

KPI	Description	Assessment method
Physical painting inspection comfort KPI	A self-report tool or questionnaire (between the baseline and validation stage) can be employed to quantify the level of comfort and satisfaction in workers after deploying the automatic vision system on the shop floor.	Work-related body-part discomfort scale [19] and adapted physical exertion scale [20]. Occupational self-efficacy [21].
Eye physical comfort KPI	The eye physical conform can be quantify by the percentage of time look a fixed object and employing a self-report tool/questionnaire changes between baseline and technology validation.	70% reduction of time spent on looking on the painted surface, as well as lower scores on Work-related body-part discomfort scale [19].
Metal fatigue KPI	Brain activity in the prefrontal cortex in terms of oxy- and deoxyhemoglobin concentration and self-report tool/questionnaire changes between baseline and technology validation time points.	30% reduction of mental fatigue and mental demand as measured by NASA TLX [22] and triangulated with physiological data capture (fNIRS)
Automatic inspection system engagement KPI	A self-report tool or questionnaire (between the baseline and validation stage) can be employed to quantify positive engagement and attitudes toward the new developed process.	Technology acceptance model 3 [23] and Trust in industrial HRC [24].

The human-centric objective of deploying automatic visual inspection system focuses in reducing physical discomfort and mental fatigue of operators on a given manufacturing process. Integrating automatic visual inspection systems, based on collaborative robots, and equipped with artificial vision capabilities for painting defects identification and location will reduce mental and physical workers' fatigue (Table 1). The AI algorithm support the decision-making process for defect detection and classification, and the augmented reality helps to communicate the position of the detected defect to the operator in order to perform the repairing operation. Collaborative robots positively influence manufacturing by reducing manual labour, minimizing exposure to hazardous materials, and enhancing ergonomics.

3 Artificial intelligence algorithms for automatic vision inspection

Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration in decision-making processes has increased considerably in recent years due to three factors [25]. First, the reduction in the cost of acquisition equipment has made data more readily available. The advancement of techniques that allow the processing of extensive data sets to discern patterns, correlations and anomalies. Finally, integration and interoperability, which foster collaboration between systems.

In the AI field, computer vision (CV) is a key area of interest that encompasses the autonomous extraction of information from visual content, such as images or videos [26]. Since a decade ago, the improvement in hardware performance has allowed CV to experience the incorporation of AI and Deep Learning (DL) techniques and as a consequence has been introduced in various sectors, such as biomedicine, the food industry, agriculture and the development of autonomous vehicles, among others [27]. In particular, one of the most frequent applications is the inspection of products in the industrial field, either during the production phase of components or during the operation of products and structures.

3.1 Deep learning algorithms

Deep learning (DL) can be considered a subfield of machine learning and artificial intelligence, which, in the last decade, has been demonstrating outstanding performance in defect detection in CV. Several algorithms have been applied for industrial manufacturing and component performance monitoring, including supervised, semi-supervised and unsupervised methods [28], [29], [30]. Supervised algorithms are trained to recognize patterns in images, which allows predicting defects in unseen images. However, this approach requires large amounts of labeled data, leading to significant economic and time costs [31]. In contrast, unsupervised learning is used when data is unlabeled, with the goal of discovering hidden patterns or structures without prior knowledge [32].

Some works propose a supervised defect detection method as in where a YOLOv3 is improved with a new feature fusion to detect eight types of defects on the paint surface of five-star office chair feet, achieving an average accuracy of 88.3% [33]. In ResNet17, a pre-trained convolutional neural network is used to classify defects in paint, obtaining 86.4% for seven types of defects [34]. Unsupervised anomaly detection can be used when labeled data is not available, assuming that most of the samples in the data set are not faulty and that faulty cases are rare. Semi-supervised algorithms combine aspects of supervised and unsupervised methods. Although unsupervised learning has shown promise in some CV applications, it is less frequently used for defect inspection compared to supervised learning, which traditionally offers superior performance. A new dataset from painted metal parts fabrication is introduced by Jezek et al. (2021), on their article evaluate the performance of current state-of-the-art unsupervised methods to detect defects in an anomaly detection approach [35]. Based on the dataset an using PatchCore an AUROC of 99.1% was achieved.

3.2 Importance of dataset

The lack of balanced data on deep learning algorithms can produce inaccurate results due to prioritisation performed by the standard loss functions [36]. Therefore, to deploy automatic DL visual inspection solutions in industrial product quality detection, a vast amount of data should be acquired, labelled and trained, increasing the algorithm's human labour and computational burden [37]. When the minority class is important, attention must be paid to the imbalance of the data. Some techniques are addressed in the recent review performed by Wang et al. (2021), dividing between under-sampling and over-sampling methods. Some examples are synthetic minority over-sampling technique (SMOTE), support vector machine (SVM), and k-nearest neighbor (KNN) [38].

3.3 Hardware selection based on the customer requirements

The accuracy, efficiency and performance of the machine vision-based visual detection equipment not only rely on the artificial intelligence algorithms, but another important parameter is the image acquisition hardware. Relate the nature of the defect (size, form, colour, etc.), inspection velocity with type of sensor, sensor size, frame rate, optical lens, working distance, field of view, and illumination system.

Fig. 1. Factors to be considered when setting up the image acquisition system.

As shown in Fig. 1, factors such as sensor size, resolution, speed and pixel size significantly impact the efficacy of AI inspection. In addition to this, the optical lens plays a crucial role in shaping contrast, minimizing aberrations and determining the working distance. These characteristics depend on factors such as wavelength, pixel pitch, focal length and field of view. The proposed image acquisition system for painting defects detection will employ Basler acA5472-5gc camera, which uses the Sony IMX183 color CMOS sensor of 20 Megapixels, pixel size $2.4 \times 2.4 \mu\text{m}$ and sensor size of $13.13 \times 8.76 \text{ mm}$. Complementing this, it is used the Fujinon Lens CF25ZA-1S F1.8 f25mm 4/3, offering a field of view (FOV) spanning approximately 30 cm in width and 20 cm in height (around 18 pixels/mm of spatial resolution). This setup enables image acquisition for defect detection on wind towers from about 50-55 cm.

To tackle the challenge of the wind tower's expansive surface area, the image acquisition will be performed in an open workshop environment characterized by poor lighting. The correct design lighting system improves visual contrast and reduce noise. For this purpose, decisions must be made about the lighting scheme, type and geometry of the illumination, as well as the brightness. Current research employs bar light model MBJ SBL-0150 LED light source, with incidence angle of 40°, due to their ease of integration, low consumption, and high lifespan.

3.4 Performance of the prediction model

To evaluate the performance of the prediction model training by DL, different metrics described below can be employed. In the case of supervised object detection, the most commonly used metric is the mean Average Precision (mAP), that provides a single number as the mean of the Average Precision (AP) values for all classes, where K represents the total number of queries in the set. This simplifies model assessment to a single metric, making mAP the preferred evaluation criterion for object detection algorithms [39]. High mAP values are necessary for industries with great added value, such as semiconductors (>0.90), while in other industries, such as the manufacturing of metal parts, these requirements are not so strict (Table 2).

Table 2. State-of-the-art works for detecting defects with YOLO in industrial fields.

Work	Field	mAP
YOLO-IMF: an improved YOLOv8 algorithm for surface defect detection in industrial manufacturing field. [39]	Packaging defect detection	0.789
Defect detection for metal base of TO-Can packaged laser diode based on improved YOLO algorithm. [40]	Metal TO-can	0.840
Toward surface defect detection in electronics manufacturing by an accurate and lightweight YOLO-style object detector. [41]	Electronics	0.928

4 Autonomous Guided Vehicles

One key difference in the wind tower for the renewable energy industry, concerning others, is the scale of the products to be manufactured. This aspect has a profound impact on the industrial processes used during production [42]. Simply moving a product through the factory poses a complex problem in itself [43]. For this reason, implementing automated inspection techniques is more challenging than regular conveyor belt-based production lines. One possible solution to overcome these issues is to make the inspection system mobile using autonomous guided vehicles (AGV). This chapter briefly describes the traditional role of AGV within the industry, the main functions they should comply with for successful integration into a production line, and the existent state-of-the-art approaches used in each regard.

4.1 AGV in industrial processes

AGV can be helpful in numerous industrial processes as a substitute for human labour. One of the most common scenarios in which AGVs are commonly used is intra-factory logistics [44]. Mobile robots are used to move materials around in warehouses. The tasks can include stock replenishment, transportation of raw materials, or preparing and dispatching customer orders [45]. The range of adaptability varies for each use case, but most require some adaptation of the existing infrastructure to facilitate AGV tasks. Regarding automatic inspection systems, the current state-of-the-art commercial-level AGV implementation still needs to be improved. In this regard, most applications are centred around aerial AGV (i.e. autonomous drones). Several use case scenarios vary from inspecting civil engineer structures like bridges or large buildings [45] to controlling agriculture fields [46].

4.2 Autonomous navigation

In general, autonomous robot navigation requires the solution of three different tasks: mapping (*What does the world look like?*), localization (*Which is my position in the world?*), and path planning (*How can I reach some position in the world?*) [47]. The solution to these tasks cannot be performed independently since each is inter-dependent of the others. For this reason, the complexity of the navigation problem has a substantial dependence on the specific scenario in which AGV need to operate and how many of the former tasks we need to solve.

On one side the whole factory can be statically mapped and the routes can be planned a priori. On the other side, AGV would need to recognise environment features to localise themselves and dynamically plan their routes accordingly. While the first scenario is usually preferred for being simpler, in most cases, factories find themselves in a middle ground between both [46].

From a high-level perspective, the AGV should be able to go across the painted surface maintaining a constant distance to the surface, for visual inspecting the wind tower. While being a relatively controlled scenario in which a partial mapping of the environment is available, the variability between different tower types and the fact that the human is still in the loop of numerous processes, makes the necessity of localisation (respect to the surface and to the world) and online computation of the route still present. With all of this in mind, there are several navigation techniques which can be used in this setting:

- **Physical anchoring.** This family of approaches rely on objects with known position to determine its position in the world and plan their route accordingly. Among this family of techniques, we can find magnetic tapes, inductive wiring, visual stickers like QR codes or RFID [48].
- **Indoors position systems.** These approaches usually rely on either mechanical or electromagnetic waves beacons to compute their position in the world. Along these position systems the Ultra-wideband (UWB), RADAR

based, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth or ultrasonic waves are some of the most used technologies (Active Bat positioning system, Lok8, etc.) [49].

- **Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping techniques (SLAM).** These approaches perform the construction of the world and the localisation in it at the same time without the need of a priori map or known anchors in the environment. The sensors used to implement SLAM are often vision based (using cameras and other related imaging techniques) and LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging or Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging) [50].

4.3 Integration within existent human and machine resources

When deploying an AGV in an industrial environment, one important factor to consider is how it will interact with both human operators and existing machinery. This is especially critical when deploying an AGV-based inspection system for windmill tower painting inspection.

On one hand, currently, the painting inspection task is performed manually by human operators. This means both human and automatic inspection will need to coexist at least for some time, and even when fully deployed, the computer vision system will continue to be fed by additional data labelled by expert operators to address subtle environmental changes over time. On the other hand, as aforementioned, the size of the products to inspect makes the deployment of NDI especially challenging. For example, to perform the inspection of the complete surface of the tower, the inspection system should be able to interact with existing equipment (e.g., rotators) to be able to scan the whole surface of the towers, including auxiliary equipment such as rotators.

For both cases, the OPC-UA communication protocol represents a modern solution to perform this type of communication [51], [52] []. This is especially true in environments where several types of devices cooperate. OPC-UA is a cross-platform, open-source standard for data exchange from sensors to cloud applications that was designed with machine automation in mind. In the case of machine vision, the VDMA has recently published a specification companion [51], [52] that describes an abstraction of a generic vision system via a common digital representation (i.e., digital twin). This enables other systems, as in this case AGV and rotators, to easily interact with vision systems.

5 Augmented Reality Platform

The Augmented Reality Platform (ARP) will allow the visualisation of the defects acquired and identified by the automatic vision system, and thanks to the shopfloor location of the AGV, it will allow the interaction with the operator to perform the repairing tasks (Fig. 2). Thanks to the ARP solutions, the painting inspector can locate the defect in the real world and repair it before sending it to the next working station.

The wind tower virtual digital twin uses the inspection data created by the artificial intelligence inspection solution and the position of the AGV to locate the defects in the

augmented reality; the AR device understands its position in relation to the inspected object. The AR device's spatial capability allows the user to be guided to the wind tower coordinates where the painting defect is present. The defect information can be superimposed in the AR windows thanks to inspection data from the automatic defect recognition solution. The AR-enhanced inspection solution can document the activities, such as repairing or the evaluation of the inspector's decision.

Fig. 2. Wind Tower Augmented Reality solution.

5.1 Main framework to deploy Augmented Reality in large surface inspection parts

The deployment of interoperable inspection technologies, robotics systems and augmented/virtual reality solutions will allow to deploy Human-centered solutions based on automated visual inspection system. The Fig. 3 describe some of the services that the AR platform will provide for inspection purposes.

- **Model Tracking Module** will be responsible for recognizing the wind tower from the cameras AR device and superimpose the inspection information onto the object.
- **AR-Enhance Inspection Controller** acts as a data backed for user interfaces, loads the inspection data for the automatic visual inspection module (Defect Store), data from tracking manufacturing order (Scenario Controller), the pose of the inspected part (Ref. Object Position Information Service), and the object CAD data is supplied by the Model Manager.
- **AR-Enhanced Inspection UI** module will combine the AGV, AR device tracking information and the defect coordinates extracted from AI algorithms to superimpose the information on the wind tower thanks to the digital twin display on the AR device.

Fig. 3. Augmented Reality diagram.

6 Conclusion

The proposed automated visual inspection framework has demonstrated that current technologies enable a symbiotic collaboration environment, where humans and robots will share a working area simultaneously without physical separation, reducing the cycle time, risks and cost compared with manual visual inspection of painting surfaces. Low quality in the manufacturing facility reduces the availability of production hours; this lost capacity reduces profitability and increases costs related to material and energy consumption and operational costs, reducing the economical manufacturing sustainability. The NDI, along with AI algorithms, Digital Twin and Augmented Reality technologies, present the ability to detect defects or lack of control on a real-time basis, and these solutions present an advantage for advancing sustainable production since improve the decision-making process and reduce the downstream quality inspection. All these inspection solutions, methods or strategies are designed to maximize flexibility, quality, and minimize lead times, inventories, and operational costs. To achieve this purposes, multimodal communication for sensor integration and control need to be addressed for adaptive control for robot execution to perform the automated visual inspection.

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